

KRAMER USULINI C++ VA C# TILLARIDA QULAY HISOBLASH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz chiziqli algebra va analitik geometriya fanidan chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini Kramer usulida yechishni hozirda rivojlanayotgan sohalardan biri bo'lmish IT sohasidagi C# va C++ dasturlash tillarida ishlab, chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini ishlashni yanayam qulay va oson bo'lgan usulini yechishni o'rganamiz.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы научимся решать систему линейных уравнений из науки линейной алгебры и аналитической геометрии методом Крамера, который является одним из развивающихся в настоящее время направлений в сфере информационных технологий, с использованием языков программирования C# и C++ для решения. система линейных уравнений, с которой более удобно и легко работать.

Ключевые слова: Крамер, C#, C++, коэффициенты, свободные члены, определитель, вспомогательный определитель.

Annotation: In this article, we will learn how to solve a system of linear equations from the science of linear algebra and analytic geometry by Cramer's method, which is one of the currently developing fields in the IT field, using C# and C++ programming languages, to solve a system of linear equations that is more convenient and easy to work with.

Keywords: Kramer, C#, C++, coefficients, free terms, determinant, auxiliary determinant

Kramer, matritsalar sistemalari bo'yicha doimiy qismatlash usulidir. Bu usulda matritsaning haqidagi n a'zolari uchun birlamchi qiymatlarni topish uchun formulalar ishlatiladi. Qo'shimcha tushunchalar bilan bu usulning C# da implementatsiyasini o'rganish uchun, Kramer usulidagi maqolalarni o'qishingiz mumkin. Bu maqolalar

sizga bu usulni qanday qo'llashni orgatib beradi. Mavjud maqolalar bilan aloqani saqlashni maslahat beraman.

Kramer usuli kompyuter dasturlashida keng qo'llaniladi va muhim funksiyalarni amalga oshirish uchun foydalaniladi. Bu usul orqali dasturchilar kamera va video qurilmalari bilan aloqani boshqarish, rasm va video ma'lumotlarini yuklash, saqlash, o'zgartirishva ulardan foydalanish mumkin.

$$\text{Ushbu uchta no'malumli tenglamalar sistemasida u } \begin{cases} a_{11}x + a_{12}y + a_{13}z = b_1 \\ a_{21}x + a_{22}y + a_{23}z = b_2 \\ a_{31}x + a_{32}y + a_{33}z = b_3 \end{cases}$$

Sistema uch-x, y va z noma'lumli chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasi deyiladi, bunda a_{11} , a_{12} , a_{13} , a_{21} , a_{22} , a_{23} , a_{31} , a_{32} , a_{33} sonlar tenglamalar sistemasining koeffitsiyentlari, b_1 , b_2 va b_3 sonlar ozod hadlar deyiladi.

Berilgan sistemaning koeffitsiyentlaridan ushbu

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

Determinantni, so'ng bu determinantning birinchi ustunidagi elementlarni ozod hadlar bilan almashtirib,

$$\Delta_x = \begin{vmatrix} b_1 & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ b_2 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ b_3 & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

Determinantni, ikkinchi ustunidagi elementlarni ozod hadlar bilan almashtirib,

$$\Delta_y = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & b_1 & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & b_2 & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & b_3 & a_{33} \end{vmatrix}$$

Determinantni, uchinchi ustunidagi elementlarni ozod hadlar bilan almashtirib,

$$\Delta_z = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & b_1 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & b_2 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & b_3 \end{vmatrix}$$

Determinantlar hosil qilamiz.

Teorema. Quyidagi

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x + a_{12}y + a_{13}z = b_1 \\ a_{21}x + a_{22}y + a_{23}z = b_2 \\ a_{31}x + a_{32}y + a_{33}z = b_3 \end{cases}$$

Tenglamalar sistemasi berilgan bo'lsin. Agar:

1) $\Delta \neq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda berilgan sistema yagona (x, y, z) yechimga ega bo'lib,

$$2) x = \frac{\Delta_x}{\Delta}, y = \frac{\Delta_y}{\Delta}, z = \frac{\Delta_z}{\Delta}$$

bo'ladi;

2) $\Delta = 0$ bo'lib, $\Delta_x \neq 0$, $\Delta_y \neq 0$, $\Delta_z \neq 0$ bo'lsa, u holda berilgan sistema yechimga ega bo'lmaydi;

3) $\Delta = \Delta_x = \Delta_y = \Delta_z = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda berilgan sistema cheksiz ko'p yechimga ega bo'ladi.

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x + a_{12}y + a_{13}z = 0 \\ a_{21}x + a_{22}y + a_{23}z = 0 \\ a_{31}x + a_{32}y + a_{33}z = 0 \end{cases}$$

Sistema $\Delta \neq 0$ da yagona $x=y=z=0$ nol(trivial)yechimga ega,

Teorema isbotini ushbu misolda ko'rib chiqsak, $\Delta = 0$ bo'lganida esa noldan farqli(notrivial) cheksiz ko'p yechimga ega. Bir jinsli sistemalarni tekshirish va yechish istalgan algebraik tenglamalar sistemalarini yechishga bag'ishlangan keyingi maqolalarimizda yoritib beramiz.

$$\begin{cases} 3x - y + 2z = 3 \\ -2x + y + 3z = 3 \\ x - 3y + 4z = -1 \end{cases}$$

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & -1 & 2 \\ -2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & -3 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 12 - 3 + 12 - 2 + 27 - 8 = 38. \Delta \neq 0.$$

Sistema yagona yechimga ega. Yechimni Kramer formulalari yordamida topamiz:

$$\Delta_x = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & -1 & 2 \\ 3 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & -1 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 12 + 3 - 18 + 2 + 27 + 12 = 38;$$

$$\Delta_y = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 3 & 2 \\ -2 & 3 & 3 \\ 1 & -1 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 76;$$

$$\Delta_z = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & -1 & 3 \\ -2 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & -3 & -1 \end{vmatrix} = 38;$$

$$x = \frac{\Delta_x}{\Delta} = \frac{38}{38} = 1; \quad y = \frac{\Delta_y}{\Delta} = \frac{76}{38} = 2; \quad z = \frac{\Delta_z}{\Delta} = \frac{38}{38} = 1.$$

Javob(1, 2, 1).

C++

```
#include <iostream>
```

```
using namespace std;
```

```
double determinant(double a, double b, double c, double d, double e, double f, double g, double h, double i) {
```

```
    return a * e * i + b * f * g + c * d * h - c * e * g - b * d * i - a * f * h;
```

```
}
```

```
int main() {
```

```
    double A[3][4];
```

```
    cout << "ax + by + cz = d:" << endl;
```

```
    for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
```

```
        cout << "a" << i + 1 << ": ";
```

```
        cin >> A[i][0];
```

```
        cout << "b" << i + 1 << ": ";
```

```
cin >> A[i][1];  
cout << "c" << i + 1 << ": ";  
cin >> A[i][2];  
cout << "d" << i + 1 << ": ";  
cin >> A[i][3];  
}  
double detA = determinant(A[0][0], A[0][1], A[0][2],  
    A[1][0], A[1][1], A[1][2],  
    A[2][0], A[2][1], A[2][2]);  
double detX = determinant(A[0][3], A[0][1], A[0][2],  
    A[1][3], A[1][1], A[1][2],  
    A[2][3], A[2][1], A[2][2]);  
double detY = determinant(A[0][0], A[0][3], A[0][2],  
    A[1][0], A[1][3], A[1][2],  
    A[2][0], A[2][3], A[2][2]);  
double detZ = determinant(A[0][0], A[0][1], A[0][3],  
    A[1][0], A[1][1], A[1][3],  
    A[2][0], A[2][1], A[2][3]);  
if(detA!=0) { double x = detX / detA, y = detY / detA, z = detZ / detA;  
    cout << "x = " << x << endl;  
    cout << "y = " << y << endl;  
    cout << "z = " << z << endl;}  
if(detA==0)
```

```
{ if(detX==0 && detY==0 && detZ==0) cout<<"natija=" <<"Cheksiz ko'p  
yechimga ega"<<endl;  
  
if(detX!=0 && detY!=0 && detZ!=0) cout<<"natija=" <<"Yechimga ega  
emas"<<endl;  
  
}  
  
return 0;  
  
}
```

Natijasi:

```
Compile Result  
  
ax + by + cz = d:  
a1: 3  
b1: -1  
c1: 2  
d1: 3  
a2: -2  
b2: 1  
c2: 3  
d2: 3  
a3: 1  
b3: -3  
c3: 4  
d3: -1  
x = 1  
y = 2  
z = 1  
  
[Process completed - press Enter]
```

C#

```
using System;  
  
using System.Linq;  
  
namespace Kramer_3_ta_nomalumli_tenglamalar_sistemasini_yechish;  
  
public static class Program
```

```
{  
  
    static double Determinant(double a, double b, double c, double d, double e,  
double f, double g, double h, double i)  
  
    {  
  
        return a * e * i + b * f * g + c * d * h - c * e * g - b * d * i - a * f * h;  
  
    }  
  
    static void Main(string[] args)  
  
    {  
  
        double[,] A = new double[3, 4];  
  
        Console. Write("ax+by+cz=d");  
  
        for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++)  
  
        {  
  
            Console. WriteLine("Equation" + (i + 1) + " ");  
  
            Console. Write("a=");  
  
            A[i, 0] = Convert. ToDouble(Console. ReadLine());  
  
            Console. Write("b=");  
  
            A[i, 1] = Convert. ToDouble(Console. ReadLine());  
  
            Console. Write("c=");  
  
            A[i, 2] = Convert. ToDouble(Console. ReadLine());  
  
            Console. Write("d=");  
  
            A[i, 3] = Convert. ToDouble(Console. ReadLine());  
  
        }  
  
        double detA = Determinant(A[0, 0], A[0, 1], A[0, 2], A[1, 0], A[1, 1],  
A[1, 2], A[2, 0], A[2, 1], A[2, 2]);
```

```
double detX = Determinant(A[0, 3], A[0, 1], A[0, 2], A[1, 3], A[1, 1],  
A[1, 2], A[2, 3], A[2, 1], A[2, 2]);
```

```
double detY = Determinant(A[0, 0], A[0, 3], A[0, 2], A[1, 0], A[1, 3],  
A[1, 2], A[2, 0], A[2, 3], A[2, 2]);
```

```
double detZ = Determinant(A[0, 0], A[0, 1], A[0, 3], A[1, 0], A[1, 1],  
A[1, 3], A[2, 0], A[2, 1], A[2, 3]);
```

```
if (detA != 0) { double X = detX / detA, Y = detY / detA, Z = detZ / detA;  
Console.WriteLine("nomalum x=" + X + " namalum y=" + Y + " namalum=" + Z +  
"");} }
```

```
if (detA == 0 && detX != 0 && detY != 0 && detZ != 0) { Console.  
WriteLine("Yagona yechimga ega"); }
```

```
if (detA == 0 && detX == 0 && detY == 0 && detZ == 0) { Console.  
WriteLine("Cheksiz ko'p yechimga ega"); }
```

```
}
```

Natijasi:

```
ax+by+cz=dEquation1  
a=3  
b=-1  
c=2  
d=3  
Equation2  
a=-2  
b=1  
c=3  
d=3  
Equation3  
a=1  
b=-3  
c=4  
d=-1  
nomalum x=1 namalum y=2 namalum=1
```

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

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